

Sample Name: dNTPs ATP mix 20uM

```

=====
Acq. Operator   : SYSTEM                      Seq. Line :    4
Sample Operator : SYSTEM
Acq. Instrument : HPLC-UV-FC                 Location  :    4
Injection Date  : 12/10/2020 1:40:21 PM      Inj       :    1
                                           Inj Volume: 50.000 µl
Method         : C:\Users\Public\Documents\ChemStation\3\Data\dNMP to dNTP yield 2020-12-10
                12-20-56\dNTP QUANTIFICATION.M (Sequence Method)
Last changed   : 12/10/2020 10:10:22 AM by SYSTEM
=====
    
```


Fraction Information

No Fractions found.

Area Percent Report

```

Sorted By      :      Signal
Multiplier     :      1.0000
Dilution       :      1.0000
Do not use Multiplier & Dilution Factor with ISTDs
    
```

Signal 1: VWD1 A, Wavelength=254 nm

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	10.515	BV R	0.1937	698.30310	55.93915	11.5200
2	10.832	VB E	0.1604	25.20037	2.29028	0.4157
3	12.974	BV R	0.1794	1461.32996	125.64979	24.1077
4	14.791	BB	0.1892	759.37390	62.13216	12.5275
5	16.243	BB	0.1905	1620.63745	131.36699	26.7358
6	18.395	BB	0.1964	1496.82385	117.67567	24.6933

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Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
Totals :				6061.66863	495.05405	

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*** End of Report ***